

Survival was not correlated with initial height ($r = 0.19$) or elongation ($r = 0.01$). Most lines elongated 0.5-2.5 mm/d. Many lines with higher elongation rate had poor survival.

The excellent survival of IR43522-37-3-3-3 may be due to rapid

elongation rather than to physiological tolerance for submergence (it does not have a donor for tolerance in its parentage). IR40931-33-1-3-2 had poor elongation but excellent submergence tolerance derived from FR13A. It was selected from the cross

BKNFR76106-16-0-1-0/IR19661-131-1-2; FR13A was a parent of BKNFR76106. IR40931-33-1-3-2 has consistently shown high submergence tolerance in screening at IRRI. □

Survival after submergence and increase in seedling height of improved breeding lines and check cultivars. IRRI, 1989.

Designation	Initial plant height (H ₁) (cm)	Elongation (H ₂ -H ₁) during submergence (cm)	Survival (%)
IR43522-37-3-3-3	23.8	6.2	70
IR40931-33-1-3-2	19.3	0.7	57
FR13A (resistant check)	26.7	1.2	53
UPR238-42-2-3-1	18.7	1.2	50
IR42205-33-1-3-3-2	21.7	0.7	50
TCA4	22.3	1.2	50
LMN111	27.5	4.5	57
Patnai 23	21.7	1.8	43
TCA214	25.8	1.0	43
TCA808	25.7	0.7	40
BKNFR76106-16-0-1-0	23.3	3.3	40
TCA48	27.5	2.0	40
IR43485-22-2-2-2	19.0	3.0	40
TCA62-10	23.5	0.7	37
Baisbish	21.5	5.5	37
TCA148-3	24.8	0.5	37
IR46292-24-2-2-1-2	25.3	4.5	37
GS302	26.2	1.0	37
IR43470-7-3-5-1	21.3	1.2	33
RAUSRR 2	27.0	2.5	33
IR43049-99-23-1-1	22.8	0.7	30
IR40931-26-3-3-5	22.0	1.0	27
Madhukar	28.0	2.2	27
Jaladhi-1	20.7	1.7	27
Rupsail	21.2	0.5	23
TCA72	23.2	1.2	23
TCA62-31-1	27.5	1.8	20
IR36	21.5	7.0	20
TCA177	24.7	1.5	20
RAUSRR 8	22.7	1.0	20
IR42 (susceptible check)	19.8	1.5	20
Moddawi Karruppan	27.5	-	17
BE3	30.2	-	13
BR8	28.3	-	13
RAUSBR 80-644-1	20.0	-	13
IR43559-25-5-3-2	20.0	-	13
Nam Sagui 19	23.3	-	10
IR46298-16-3-3-3	23.5	-	10
Wagwag	25.2	-	10
TCA258	24.8	-	10
Jhingsail	19.3	-	10
TCA80-4	19.0	-	10
IR11141-6-1-4	18.7	-	10
RAUSBR 30-603-14-1-1	22.2	-	7
Mahsuri	23.0	-	3
IR40905-RRR-21	20.0	-	3
TCA 196	20.0	-	3
BR9	21.2	-	0
RAUSRR 10	18.3	-	0
Ratakuta	23.8	-	0
RAUSRR 5	25.5	-	0
TCA227	21.2	-	0
TCA279	22.3	-	0
CR1009	20.2	-	0
BR34	22.2	-	0
LSD (0.05)	0.9	1.2	10

Adverse temperature tolerance

New synthetic phytohormone analog promotes leaf photosynthetic rate of rice after chilling

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We investigated the effects of a new synthetic analog of the phytohormone abscisic acid (ABA) (developed by BASF, Ludwigshafen, FRG; coded LAB 173711) on leaf photosynthetic rate of rice plants after chilling.

ABA, LAB 173711, growth retardant tetcyclacis, and a combination of LAB 173711 and tetcyclacis were applied as a 10⁻³ mol/liter of aqueous foliar spray to IR36 plants in a controlled environment (12 h photoperiod, 26/21 °C, 70% relative humidity). At 24 h after spraying, the plants were subjected to a 2 or 3 d chilling treatment at 5 °C, kept at a transitional temperature of 23 °C for 12 h, and transferred back to the original temperature.

At 2, 9, and 24 d after chilling, net leaf photosynthetic rate was measured using a steady state CO₂/H₂O porometer (Walz, Effeltrich, West Germany) and a BINOS infrared gas analyzer (Heraeus, Hanau, West Germany).

In untreated plants, chilling caused visible injuries (leaf necrosis, death) and almost total growth cessation. Injury was still evident after 23 d recovery. Plants pretreated with

ABA, LAB 173711, or a combination of LAB 173711 and tetcyclacis had fully recovered 23 d after treatment. Pretreatment with tetcyclacis alone produced intermediate effects.

Chilling reduced leaf photosynthesis in all treatments, most drastically in untreated controls (90% reduction after 2 d recovery) (see figure). Differences among treatments were most significant after 9 d recovery: photosynthetic rates had returned to the original values in plants pretreated with both LAB 173711 and tetcyclacis; control values were lower by 60%. Pretreatment with LAB 173711 and tetcyclacis led to significantly faster recovery than did pretreatment with ABA or LAB 173711 alone.

Chemical analogs of ABA, particularly in combination with tetcyclacis, represent a potentially powerful tool to prevent chilling injury in rice plants. □

Changes in net photosynthetic rate (A) in IR36 rice plants during recovery from 2 d chilling at 5 °C, IRRI, 1988. Means ± SE of 8 measurements.

Adverse soils tolerance

Effect of salinity on rice germination and seedling growth

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We evaluated the relative salinity tolerance of BG350 an improved variety commonly grown on saline soils. Salinity-tolerant traditional variety Pokkali was the check.

Irrigation water (EC 0.25 dS/m) was used as the laboratory medium. Electrical conductivity was adjusted to 0.25, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 dS/m by adding table salt. Twenty seeds were kept in each solution in petri dishes, with three replications. Water volume was maintained by adding solution.

Effect of salinity on rice root and shoot growth. Weerawila, Sri Lanka.

EC (dS/m)	Root length (cm)		Seedling height (cm)	
	BG350	Pokkali	BG350	Pokkali
0.25	2.1	5.9	2.1	4.6
1.0	2.4	3.9	2.2	4.2
2.0	2.3	3.5	2.5	3.5
3.0	1.5	2.5	2.3	2.5
4.0	1.0	1.7	2.0	1.6
6.0	0.6	1.0	1.3	0.6
8.0	Traces		0.6	1.0
LSD (0.05)	0.30	0.61	0.59	0.59

After 5 d, germinated seeds were counted and root length and seedling height measured.

BG350 performance was similar to that of salinity-tolerant Pokkali (see table). No seeds germinated at EC 10 and 12 dS/m. All seeds germinated at

EC 8 dS/m and below.

Root length decreased significantly at EC 2 dS/m and above. Neither variety produced roots at EC 8 dS/m. Seedling height decreased significantly at salinity levels above EC 4 dS/m. □

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